

Developing Green In-Built Algorithms for Colorizing LAS Data in GIS Environments

SGIS V.R TECHNOLOGY

7/19/2024

Developing Green In-built Algorithms for Colorizing LAS Data in GIS Environments

SGIS v.R Technology

Keywords:

LIDAR & Remote Sensing, GIS, Green Software Development, New Algorithms, Colorize LAS Data;

Why Colorize a Point Cloud?

Standard point clouds are incredibly useful, but colorizing them makes them even more valuable. Adding colors and near-infrared values from images to LAS points creates an immersive, photorealistic display. This enhanced visual feedback offers deeper insights into the characteristics of the point cloud, which is especially helpful for tasks like interactive data classification, digitizing new features, and setting reference points for 3D distance measurements.

SGIS v.R Technology:

Let's begin by importing the LAS file into the SGIS v.R software:

Fig.1 A LiDAR point cloud and a tile-based map displayed in SGIS Desktop v.R.

Previously, we incorporated Google Satellite Imagery as a background layer. The algorithm seamlessly integrates with both image layers and tile map service layers. To showcase its efficiency and speed, we will colorize the LAS file using the base tile map as the underlying backdrop.

Fig.2 The 'Colorize LAS' function colorizes lidar data through raster overlay.

We need to proceed to the 'Colorize LAS' function. To access it, we simply click on it.

Fig.3 The dialog window for the 'Colorize LAS' function, allowing users to select their LAS layer and raster/TMS layer from the lists. Once selections are made, clicking 'Colorize' initiates the process.

Once the function is activated, a new dialog window appears. This window allows the user to select their LAS layer and their raster/TMS layer from the respective lists. After making these selections, we simply click on 'Colorize'.

Fig.4 The LAS point cloud colorized in RGB.

Here's an analysis table based on the efficiency of executing the colorization algorithm in SGIS v.R software and its alignment with Green Software Development and Green IT principles:

Criteria	SGIS v.R Technology (Colorize LAS)
Algorithm Execution Efficiency	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Speed: Optimized for fast performance, even with large datasets. ▪ Input Requirements: Supports both image layers and tile map service layers. ▪ Integration: A new algorithm independent of rapislasso, integrated directly into SGIS Desktop, providing a seamless workflow. ▪ Usability: Intuitive interface with straightforward options, suitable for both new and experienced users.
Green Software Development	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Resource Efficiency: Designed to be resource-efficient, reducing system load. ▪ Energy Consumption: Lower energy consumption due to optimized algorithms. ▪ Optimization: Focus on minimizing energy use and maximizing processing efficiency.
Green IT Alignment	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> ▪ Environmental Impact: Lower due to efficient processing and reduced energy consumption. ▪ Sustainability Practices: Emphasis on sustainable software development practices, aligning with Green IT principles.

Fig.5 An analysis table evaluating the efficiency of the colorization algorithm execution in SGIS v.R software and its alignment with Green Software Development and Green IT principles.